

Impact Of Various Digital Health Tools on Glycemic Control and Medication Adherence Among Diabetes Mellitus: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Background: The effectiveness of digital interventions in improving glycaemic control and medication adherence among patients with diabetes remains unclear. This study aimed to evaluate the impact of such interventions on these outcomes. **Methods:** A comprehensive search was performed across PubMed, Scopus, Embase, BMJ, BioMed Central, and Google Scholar to identify randomized controlled trials (RCTs) involving digital interventions for diabetes mellitus patients. Data were extracted independently, and the risk of bias was assessed. A meta-analysis was conducted using the Cochrane RevMan 5.4 program. **Results:** A total of 3,040 patients from six trials were included, and the overall mean difference and p-values were 0.07 (p=0.76) for HbA1c in %, 0.09 (p=0.74) for FBS in mg/dl, and -0.01 (p=1.00) for medication adherence. **Conclusions:** The meta-analysis found no significant effect of digital interventions on HbA1c, FBS, or medication adherence, though individual trials showed some variability. However, digital interventions have the potential to improve glycaemic control and health outcomes. Digital health platforms can aid diabetes management, but users should exercise caution and focus on self-education.

Keywords: Digital Intervention, Medication Adherence, Glycaemic control, Diabetes mellitus, Systematic Review and Meta-analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The digital method describes the use of social media, mobile phone applications, the Internet or other digitally connected technology; this method is becoming increasingly popular in the creation, promotion, and distribution of health interventions¹. The development of digital media and communication technologies has enhanced access to information, and an increasing share of health-related information is obtained via the internet^{2,3}. The internet provides rapid and easy access to a great amount of up-to-date information and facilitates communication with health care specialists through various media platforms such as social networking websites, messengers, and video streaming services⁴. In 2019, the World Health Organization (WHO) published evidence-based guidelines for digital health initiatives. An emerging body of evidence demonstrates that digital health interventions improve

diabetes prevention and treatment adherence¹. Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is a significant and developing disease in 2019, an estimated 463 million people were living with it, accounting for 9.3% of the global adult population aged 20 to 79. This figure is predicted to rise to 578 million (10.2%) in 2030 and 700 million (10.9%) by 2045. In 2019, the prevalence of diabetes in women is expected to be 9.0%, while men will be 9.6%. According to the 10th edition of the IDF Diabetes Atlas, the estimated prevalence of diabetes would rise by 19.9% (111.2 million) as the population ages (65 to 79)^{5,6}. Until now, DM has been uncontrollable and long-term condition due to a lack of adherence which can lead to various complications. This study focuses on digital intervention to improve glycemic control and medication adherence. Some recent studies, including systematic reviews, have concluded that there is evidence and a positive effect on the use of digital interventions in clinical practice for monitoring and tracking individuals with diabetes

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and their risk factors, as well as assisting healthcare professionals in the treatment of these patients^{7,10}. There is significant interest in the possibility of digital innovations as a low-cost and scalable approach of providing continuous guidance to people with long-term health issues, allowing them to better adherence to prescribed health behaviour changes and achieve health benefits. Digital based therapies allow users to receive real-time guidance on health behaviour patterns that optimise their long-term health⁸. In this review, we evaluate the use of digital intervention to improve glycaemic control and medication adherence among diabetes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design

This systematic research and meta-analysis were reported according to the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta Analyses) guidelines⁹.(FIGURE 1)

Search strategy

We performed a systematic search of the PubMed, Scopus, and Embase databases, as well as other sources such as BMJ, BioMed Central, and Google Scholar from 1st January 2011 to 31st March 2024. The following search terms were used: digital intervention, diabetes mellitus, medication adherence, glycemic control, RCT, mobile apps (m health and e health), text and SMS messaging, and web health.

Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

We included studies based on the following criteria:

- Participants with Diabetes Mellitus;
- Study participants greater than 18 years;
- Randomized clinical trials design at least 1 month.
- Free full-text article
- Studies conducted only on human subjects

Exclusion Criteria:

We excluded studies based on the following criteria:

- Study participants less than 18 years;
- Excluded posters, commentaries, protocols, theses, and duplication
- Other than RCT are excluded
- Reviews, non-English language studies, non-human studies

Data extraction

Two reviewers independently extract the data from each eligible study. We resolve any disagreements by discussion, or by consultation with a third reviewer.

This hypothesis based on the PICO format, **Population** – both female and male with diabetes mellitus, **Intervention** - Digital intervention, **Comparison** - Trials will be included if the digital intervention is compared against usual care, **Outcomes**: To improve glycemic control by HbA1c and FBS and Adherence to Medication by using questionnaires and **Basic information**- First author, publication year, country, sample size, age, gender;

Assessment of study quality

The risk of bias of included studies was assessed in version 2 of the Cochrane risk of bias tool; which include selection bias D1, performance bias D2, detection bias D3, attrition bias D4, reporting bias D5 and Overall bias. The responses for an overall risk of bias assessment were low risk of bias, some concerns, and high risk of bias¹¹ (FIGURE 2).

Statistical analysis

The Cochrane RevMan 5.4 tool was used to perform the analysis. Data were pooled using random-effect models of presence and the absence of heterogeneity in the RevMan program. For continuous variables, mean difference is an effective indicator. The heterogeneity between study results was examined using Chi-square at the test level, and I² statistic and corresponding p-value¹¹. For HbA1c, an I² statistic exceeding 97% with p < 0.00001 was indicated as

considerable heterogeneity and statistically significant difference (FIGURE 3). For FBS, an I^2 statistic exceeding 0% with $p > 0.40$ was considered as low-heterogeneity and no statistically significant difference (FIGURE 4). For Medication Adherence, an I^2 statistic exceeding 0% with $p > 0.92$ was considered as minimal heterogeneity and no statistically significant difference (FIGURE 5).

RESULTS

Study selection

A total of 3,317 studies has been identified during the search of PubMed (2958), Scopus (356), and other sources³. This study was examined after the duplicates were removed (1317). Following title and abstract screening, 1069 studies were excluded after applying selection criteria and retrieval requests for reports (248); however, reports were not retrieved (215). Reports assessed for eligibility 33 of these 27 records were excluded due to insufficient information, with six studies included for systematic review and meta-analysis and one research excluded for meta-analysis. (FIGURE 1)

Study characteristics

In this study, six RCTs met our selection criteria and were included. A total of 3,040 participants were included, with 1,269 being male and 1,771 being female, with females greater than males. The sample size varies from 30 to 1119. The participant's ages ranged from 18 to 69. The most of the studies were prospective, followed by RCTs. The research was undertaken in Spain, the United States, East and South Africa, the Netherlands, and Korea, with studies spanning 2020-2024. The digital interventions used include mHealth, BT-001, SMS text messaging and Webpage. The above details were mentioned in the TABLE I.

Assessment of risk of bias in RCTs

The quality of RCTs were assessed by using Cochrane risk of bias tool (version 2). 6 RCTs were assessed for risk of bias, and high risk was found in one study for selection bias followed by some concern was found in same study for overall bias and show low risk in

performance, attrition, and detection bias five studies shows low risk in all type of bias. (FIGURE 2)

Effect of digital intervention on glycaemic control

HbA1c (%)

In this study, two studies showed there is significant difference of baseline to follow up period between the intervention and control group. Judith Hsia et.al (2022) found that, the baseline HbA1c was 8.2(0.1) and 8.1(0.1) in intervention group (BT-001) and control group. After 6 months follow up change in HbA1c was -0.28 and +0.11 in intervention group (BT-001) and control group($p < 0.0001$). You-Bin Lee et.al (2023) found that, the baseline HbA1c was (Group-B, C) = 7.47(0.38), 7.44(0.40) and (Group-A) = 7.45(0.36) in intervention group (digital integrated health care platform) and control group. After 48 weeks follow up change in HbA1c was (Group-B, C) = 7.20(0.64), 7.0(0.66) and (Group-A) = 7.52(0.81) in intervention group (digital integrated health care platform) and control group($p = 0.5829$). Other three studies showed there is no significant difference of baseline to follow up period between the intervention and control group. Rocío Zamanillo-Campos et.al (2023), found that the baseline HbA1c was 8.1(7.7-8.7) and 8.0(7.6-8.8) in intervention group (mHealth) and control group. After 12 months follow up change in HbA1c was 7.5(6.7-8.2) and 7.4(6.7-8.3) in intervention group (mHealth) and control group($p = 0.75$). A Farmer et.al (2021), the baseline HbA1c was 10.1(3.4) and 10.2(3.6) in intervention group (SMS text) and control group. After 12 months follow up change in HbA1c was -1.15 and -1.19 in intervention group (SMS text) and control group($p < 0.0001$). Kimberly R. Azelton et.al (2021) found that, the baseline HbA1c was 8.2(1.8) and 8.3(1.6) in intervention group (SMS) and control group. After 4 weeks follow up change in HbA1c was 7.7(1.9) and 8.3(1.7) in intervention group (SMS) and control group($p = 0.561$). The above details were mentioned in the TABLE II. Over all, the mean difference of all studies included were 0.07. An I^2 statistic exceeding 97% with $p = 0.76$ was indicated as considerable heterogeneity (FIGURE 3) and no statistically significant difference.

FBS (mg/dl)

After exposure to their intervention, FBS were lower in the intervention group compared with the control group was reported in two studies. Judith Hsia et.al (2022) found that, the baseline FBS was 9.4(3.2) and 9.3(3.0) in intervention group (BT-001) and control group. After 6 months follow up change in FBS was -0.68 and -0.07 in intervention group (BT-001) and control group($p=0.029$). You-Bin Lee et.al (2023) found that, the baseline FBS was (Group-B, C) = 148.16(25.48), 148.84(23.24) and (Group-A) = 143.88(24.7) in intervention group (digital integrated health care platform) and control group. After 48 weeks follow up change in FBS was (Group-B, C) = -2.65(27.41), -12.79(32.14) and (Group-A) = -0.70(26.66) in intervention group (digital integrated health care platform) and control group($p=0.5249$) were mentioned in the TABLE III. Over all, the mean difference of all studies included were 0.09. An I^2 statistic exceeding 0% with $p > 0.74$ was considered as low-heterogeneity and no statistically significant difference (FIGURE 4).

Effect of digital intervention on medication adherence

Adherence to anti-diabetic medication there was a statistically significant improvement in the intervention group compared to control group was reported in two studies. Rocío Zamanillo-Campos et.al(2023) found that, the baseline MA was 205(55.3%) and 194(52.3%) in intervention group (mHealth) and control group. After 12 months follow up MA was 220(65.9%) and 197(57.9%) in intervention group (mHealth) and control group($p=0.029$). A Farmer et.al (2021) found that, the baseline MA was -11.5(31.18) and -1.19(30.74) in intervention (SMS text) and control group($p=0.258$). After 12 months follow up MA was 22.7(2.6) and 22.7(2.8) in intervention (SMS text) and control group($p=0.258$). The TABLE IV included the mentioned information. Over all, the mean difference of all studies included were -0.00. An I^2 statistic exceeding 0% with $p=1.00$ was considered as minimal heterogeneity and no statistically significant difference (FIGURE 5).

DISCUSSION

This systematic review and meta-analysis found six RCTs that evaluated the effect of digital intervention. DiabeText, a tailored mHealth intervention to enhance T2DM self-management, has no significant influence on glycaemic control, medication possession ratio, or lifestyle behavior following a 12 months follow-up period. However, DiabeText was linked to increased adherence to antidiabetic medicine, diabetes self-efficacy, and health related quality of life. The findings revealed that some SMS interventions were beneficial in lowering HbA1c(12). The DiabeText study was linked to higher diabetic self-efficacy and health-related quality of life. However, existing evidence is limited and conflicting, with some research reporting considerable gains and others not. Generally, participants were satisfied with DiabeText intervention. Two participants had anxiety and remaining 332 participants did not reported any adverse events^{12,13,14}. BT-001 arm compared to the control arm exhibited significantly lower HbA1c levels at 90 days and, also measure the secondary outcomes like weight, BP and plasma lipids were lower in the intervention group compare with control group¹⁵. This BT-001 supplement medication by utilizing the user's strong relationship with their devices. Manual input, meal reporting, physical activity, and tailored feedback all contribute to engagement, making this a scalable option for better glycemic control. The adverse events reported by subjects in both control and intervention group like headache, and hypoglycaemia with most mild or moderate in severity. Two subjects had hypoglycaemia were reported in intervention group and none in control group. None of the adverse events were not reported by app use¹⁶. The StAR2D (SMS-Text Adherence Support for Type 2 Diabetes) SMS messages did not significantly improve glycaemic control in type 2 diabetes patients. However, there was some evidence this has a significant clinical influence on blood pressure and treatment outcomes. Text messages alone may not be effective for glycaemic control without multi-modal health system strengthening and self-management assistance^{17,18,19}. The intervention combines patient-driven outcomes with health coaching strategies, emphasizing diet, access to care, and medication adherence. Healthy at home digital coaching to type 2 diabetes patients in control group were median increase of 21.8% progression of insulin resistance as compared to

median decrease of 3.7% in the intervention group. The intervention combines patient-driven outcomes with health coaching strategies, emphasizing diet, access to care, medication adherence, stress reduction, and social connection. The study discovered that simple, attainable goals tailored to a patient's environment, stage of change, health literacy, and resources can have an impact. The three-month digital health coaching intervention cost \$400 per participant, with forecasts indicating that the cost might be reduced to \$270 each patient^{20,21}. Real Time Medication Monitoring (RTMM) combines SMS (Short Message Service) reminders for forgotten medications with real-time monitoring of patient's medication consumption. That SMS reminders to diabetes patients with suboptimal adherence to achieve higher adherence levels, it can be considered for various patient populations to support their medication use and improve their adherence²². Use of an integrated digital healthcare platform to diabetes patient in intervention group there was decrease in HbA1c from baseline to 24 and 48 weeks in group B and C than control (group A). The group B and C exhibited greater weight loss than group A from baseline to week 48. Therefore, use of an AI driven dietary management resulted in better glycemia and more weight loss. AI-driven dietary control increased weight loss and glycemia without changing the frequency of hypoglycemia episodes. Additionally, compared to regular diabetic care, the study indicated that using the platform with sporadically applied personal CGM (Continuous Glucose Monitor) and input from medical professionals resulted in better glycemia and more durable weight loss for 48 weeks. The results imply that, similar to other glucose-lowering treatments, interventions that include patient education and tailored feedback may have a stronger overall impact on glycemia in those with poorly managed diabetes²³. Future research is required to determine how to maximize the advantages of mHealth interventions, particularly on physiological outcomes such as glycaemic control. Further investigation is needed to understand how individual demographic, socioeconomic, behavioral, and clinical characteristics contribute to patient engagement and the efficacy of mHealth tools for diabetes. Also, more research is needed to identify the necessary health-care and self-management components, as well as tailored digital communication methods, to promote

diabetes adherence^{13,14}. Future research can improve the long-term clinical efficacy, accessibility, scalability, and cost-effectiveness of comprehensive digital health coaching. Finally, the period of span of the enrolled trials in the meta-analysis varied significantly. The meta-analysis found no effect on HbA1c, FBS or Medication Adherence. Individual study trials did, however, reveal changes in HbA1c and FBS levels, as well as medication adherence. The use of digital intervention in health communication may provide medical services over long periods of time to improve clinical patient outcomes by quick access to diabetes care and medical information²⁴. Social media platforms are playing an increasingly important role in public health communication. However, the information provided by these platforms can sometimes be low standard²⁵. As a result, it is critical for information providers, particularly medical experts, to give a more full and accurate representation of information while avoiding misleading or incomplete content. Furthermore, social media sites have a regulatory responsibility to ensure the quality of information available to the public. It is our responsibility to make positive recommendations for the use of social media platforms²⁶.

CONCLUSION

The meta-analysis discovered no significant impact of digital interventions on HbA1c, FBS, or medication adherence. However, individual trial results did show variations in medication adherence and FBS. The digital intervention has a great potential as a scalable and convenient tool to promote medication adherence and change in glycaemic control, but also had an effect in lowering HbA1c, weight loss, change in BP and alteration in lipid profiles. Health communication has expanded access to information and the amount of health-related information received via various digital platforms. The public should exercise caution when seeking DM-related information on these platforms, and actively promote self-education. Implementing a digital platform for integrated health care using health communication would assist diabetics better manage their condition. Digital based patient education for diabetes provides a continuous monitoring and improves adherence to medication and control glycaemic index.

DECLARATION

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Not applicable

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There is no conflict of interest in this study

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Code availability:

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Authors' contribution:

VA and RK independently screened titles and abstracts and assessed the full texts of all identified articles for eligibility. VA and RK independently extracted data from the included articles. VA and RK independently assess the risk of bias of the included articles. PR verified the extracted data and performed the statistical analysis. VA and RK writing the manuscript. PR read and approved the final manuscript.

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TABLES:

TABLE I: Characteristics of included studies:

Study	Sample size	Country	Age	Gender	Intervention vs Control	Follow up	Patient Characteristics
Rocío Zamanillo-Campos (2023)	742	Spain	>18	F=309 M=433	mHealth vs Usual care	12 months	T2DM with glycemic control (HbA1c >7.5%)
Judith Hsia(2022)	669	United states	M-58	F=366 M=303	BT-001 vs Control app	6 months	T2DM with HbA1c 7 to 11%
A Farmer(2021)	1119	South Africa East Africa	M-57.1	F=782 M=337	SMS text messaging vs usual care	12 months	T2DM with age >18 who taking oral Glucose-lowering medication
Kimberly R. Azelton(2021)	30	United states	18 to 65	F=15 M=15	SMS vs usual care	4 weeks	T2DM with HbA1c (6.5% or higher in the past 12 months)
Marcia Vervloet(2011)	207	Netherlands	18 to 65	NR	SMS, Webpage intervention vs usual care	6 months	T2DM with using oral antidiabetic medication for at least last one year.
You-Bin Lee(2023)	273	Korea	19 to 69	F=92 M=181	Group A received routine diabetes care vs Group B used the digital integrated health care platform by themselves vs Group C used the platform with feedback from medical staff and intermittently applied personal continuous glucose monitoring.	48 weeks	T2DM who had been taking a constant dose of one or more oral antidiabetic agents with HbA1c (7 – 8.5 %)

M, mean age; F, female; M, male; NR, not reported;

TABLE II: Result of HbA1c

Study	Intervention group		Control group		P value
	Participants (n)	HbA1c (%)	Participants(n)	HbA1c (%)	
Rocío Zamanillo-Campos (2023)	B=371 F=334	Median (IQR) B=8.1(7.7-8.7) F=7.5(6.7-8.2)	B=371 F=340	B=8.0(7.6-8.8) F=7.4(6.7-8.3)	0.75
A Farmer(2021)	B=558 F=510	B=10.1(3.4) F= -1.15	B=561 F=512	B=10.2(3.6) F= -1.19	<0.0001
Kimberly R. Azelton (2021)	B=20 F=14	B=8.2(1.8) F=7.7(1.9)	B=25 F=16	B=8.3(1.6) F=8.3(1.7)	0.561
Judith Hsia(2022)	B=326 F=265	B=8.2(0.1) F= -0.28	B=343 F=304	B=8.1(0.1) F= +0.11	< 0.0001
You-Bin Lee(2023)	B (Group-B, C) =97,98 F (Group-B, C) = 89, 86	B (Group-B, C) =7.47(0.38),7.44(0.40) F (Group-B, C) =7.20(0.64), 7.0(0.66)	B(Group-A) = 99 F(Group-A) =89	B(Group-A) =7.45(0.36) F(Group-A) =7.52(0.81)	0.5829

Data are mean (SD); B, baseline; F, follow up; IQR, interquartile range;

TABLE III: Results of FBS

Study	Intervention group		Control group		P value
	Participants(n)	FBS (mg/dl)	Participants(n)	FBS (mg/dl)	
Judith Hsia(2022)	B=326 F=265	B=9.4(3.2) F= -0.68	B=343 F=304	B=9.3(3.0) F= -0.07	0.029
You-Bin Lee(2023)	B (Group-B, C) = 97,98 F (Group-B, C) = 89, 86	B (Group-B, C) = 148.16(25.48), 148.84(23.24) F (Group-B, C) = -2.65(27.41), -12.79(32.14)	B(Group-A) = 99 F(Group-A) = 89	B(Group-A) =143.88(24.7) F(Group-A) = -0.70(26.66)	0.5249

Data are mean (SD); B, baseline; F, follow up;

TABLE IV: Results of Medication Adherence

Study	Intervention group		Control group		P value
	Participants (n)	Medication Adherence	Participants (n)	Medication Adherence	
Rocío Zamanillo-Campos (2023)	B=371 F=334	B=205(55.3%) * F=220(65.9%) *	B=371 F=340	B=194(52.3%) * F=197(57.9%) *	0.029
A Farmer(2021)	B=558 F=510	B= -11.5(31.18) ** F= 22.7(2.6) **	B=561 F=512	B= -1.19(30.74) ** F=22.7(2.8) **	0.258

* number of participants (%); ** mean (SD); B, baseline; F, follow up;

